

On Civil Engineering – A Project of Unified Alert System

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ABSTRACT

We present the unified system based upon Ford-Fulkerson maximum flow method for solving the civil engineering problems like flooding and human evacuation during earthquakes or other disasters.

METHOD

We develop the maximum flow network on map using any applicable source and present each cell with the incoming or outgoing edges as of the each of the bordering cells on the map.

The maximum flow applied to the above-described model gives the result of simple prediction scheme according to which the residue flow can be pushed forward as well as backward, and the possible dangerous zones with blocking flow can be detected and successfully mapped to the physical map where the ecological disaster happens.

At each model we give the maximum capacity as the maximum capacity of the fluid or human factor.

CONCLUSION

We presented the safe method for detecting possible bottlenecks during flooding and evacuation which can lead to a more humanistic approach in science and engineering.

REFERENCES

Kyi, Myint Than, and Lin Lin Naing. "Application of Ford-Fulkerson algorithm to maximum flow in water distribution pipeline network." *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications (IJSRP)* 8.12 (2018): 306-310.